

SAVANNA SOIL COMPACTION, WETNESS AND DEPTH PERTURB IN THE KOSTIAKOV EQUATION PARAMETERS

EFFECTOS DE LA COMPACTACIÓN, HUMEDAD Y PROFUNDIDAD DE UN SUELO DE SABANA SOBRE LOS PARÁMETROS DE LA ECUACIÓN DE KOSTIAKOV

AMÉRICO HOSSNE GARCÍA*, JESÚS MÉNDEZ NATERA, ISMARIEL JOSEFITA SMITH,
PEDRO VÁSQUEZ LEZAMA, LUIS LEIVA, ALEXANDER GIL

*Universidad de Oriente, Núcleo de Monagas, Escuela de Ingeniería Agronómica,
Departamento de Ingeniería Agrícola, Campus Los Guaritos, Maturín, Venezuela*

*Correspondencia: Américo Hossne García , Email: hossnegarciaamerico@gmail.com / americohossne@cantv.net

ABSTRACT

Infiltration processes of agricultural soils have been extensively studied due to multiple applications; and for this, several analytical equations are available. An equation widely used is Kostiakov for its practical use. In spite of the weaknesses of the model, many researchers have employed it to study the infiltration processes in soils of the temperate and tropical regions. The objectives were to investigate the effects of moisture, soil depth, and compaction on the characteristic constants “*a*”, and “*b*” in the Kostiakov equation. The experimental unit consisted of nine polyvinyl cylinders, 15.24 cm in diameter and 20 cm height, with a soil volume of 2.50 kg deposited in each cylinder. Statistical analysis was organized under a randomized block design with three replications and three factors: humidity with five levels (3, 6, 9, 12 and 15%), soil depth (0-15, 15-30 and 45-60) and compaction with three levels (0, 13 and 26 blows). It could be concluded that the relation between the instantaneous infiltration and compaction, and infiltration and bulk density are inversely proportional. Parameter “*a*” influenced infiltration more than “*b*”. Soil texture and structure influenced “*b*” more than wetness. Wetness influenced “*a*” more than compaction and soil depth. Kostiakov parameters have physical relations to soil texture and structure. The equations forms should not be freely used in any soil, unless the constants characteristic for that particular soil are first determined. It is necessary to study in depth on the applicability and precision of the infiltration equations, since the parameters of the equation and performance vary for different soils.

KEY WORDS: Surface response, Proctor test, equation analysis.

RESUMEN

La infiltración de suelos agrícolas ha sido estudiada ampliamente por múltiples aplicaciones; y para ello existen varias ecuaciones disponibles. La ecuación de Kostiakov es pródigamente utilizada. Muchos investigadores la han empleado para estudiar la infiltración en suelos de diferentes regiones. Los objetivos consistieron en evaluar efectos de la humedad, la profundidad y la compactación sobre las constantes “*a*” y “*b*” de la ecuación de Kostiakov. La unidad experimental consistió en nueve cilindros, 15,24 cm de diámetro y 20 cm de altura, con un volumen de suelo de 2,50 kg. El análisis estadístico se organizó bajo diseño de bloques al azar con tres repeticiones y tres factores: humedad con cinco niveles (3, 6, 9, 12 y 15%), profundidad del suelo (0-15, 15-30 y 45-60 cm) y compactación con tres (0, 13 y 26 golpes). Se pudo concluir que la relación entre la infiltración instantánea y la compactación, así como la infiltración y la densidad aparente son inversamente proporcionales. El parámetro “*a*” influyó en la infiltración más que el “*b*”. La textura del suelo y la estructura influyeron en “*b*” más que la humedad. La humedad influyó en “*a*” más que la compactación y la profundidad del suelo. Los parámetros de Kostiakov tienen relaciones físicas con la textura y estructura del suelo. No debería utilizarse libremente las formas de ecuaciones en ningún suelo, a menos que las características de ese suelo en particular se determinen en primer lugar. Es necesario estudiar en profundidad sobre la aplicabilidad y precisión de las ecuaciones de infiltración, ya que los parámetros de la ecuación y el rendimiento varían para diferentes suelos.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Superficie de respuesta, método Proctor, análisis de la ecuación.

INTRODUCTION

Mathematical models have become increasingly popular in the research and management of soil water flow and transport processes. The extensive interest in the Kostiakov equation stems from its simplicity, ease of determining values of the two constants from measured infiltration data, and its reasonable fit to

infiltration data for many soils over short time periods. Infiltration forced by both gravity and matric potential. The drier soil has greater matric potential pulling water in, and more porosity available to hold that water. Water moves into soil pores due to gradients in water content and potentials, and this is usually from a wet soil to a dry one. The ability of pores to conduct water mainly by pore sizes,

continuity, and distribution of the pores in the soil. Soil pore sizes classified into macro (non-capillary) pores, coarse capillary pores and fine capillary pores (Baver & Gardner 1972). Non-capillary pores represented as rapidly draining pores, while the coarse capillary pores represented by the slow draining pores and water holding pores (Amer 2009). Pressure head corresponding with the cut off between capillary and non-capillary pores varies widely, ranging from 0.1 kPa to 10 kPa (Marshall 1956, Beven & Germann 1982). Dry soils have greater matric potential absorbing water, and greater porosity to hold water (Strock 2015). Mara (2016) reported that pore diameter ≥ 30 microns (0.03 mm) hold no water due to the effect of the attractive force of gravity. Kostiakov (1932) indicated that the equation is no longer applicable once the characteristic steady infiltration rate has been attained. Infiltration variability poses a significant problem for the performance of surface irrigation systems. Not only does it reduce the existing and potential irrigation performance it also limits the ability to specify improved irrigation strategies. The nature of soil properties does not facilitate direct measurement of the infiltration function. In addition, many of the soil physical measurement techniques do not re-create the same physical phenomena and therefore cannot reflect the behavior of a soil furrow irrigated. Hence, there is a genuine need to estimate the parameters of the chosen infiltration function using measured field data. The high variance of soil properties means that these measurements must be collected during or close as possible to the irrigation event using a representative sample of the field area (Dingman 2002, Haghazari *et al.* 2015). The objectives were to investigate the effects of moisture, soil depth, and compaction on the characteristic constants “*a*”, and “*b*” in the Kostiakov infiltration equation with a view of adapting this equation.

Theory

Poulovassilis *et al.* (1989) stated that many empirical or semi-empirical equations exist for describing the relationship between the cumulative infiltration and the infiltration time, during the process of vertical infiltration of water into the soil mass. Duru *et al.* (2005) posited that Kostiakov was apparently the first to propose an empirical equation. One of the best-known models to assess the behavior of soil water infiltration is Kostiakov developed in 1932 (Kostiakov 1932, Forero 2000, Holzapfel & Matta 2005, Weber & Apestegui 2016). According to Ahuja *et al.* (2007) this equation applies only for early to intermediate infiltration times before gravity begins to dominate and the infiltration rate

approaches a constant value. Kostiakov equation is valid when the infiltration rate is higher than the saturated hydraulic conductivity of the soil (Mazloom & Foladmand 2013).

Kostiakov equation symbolized by Equation 1, “*i*” infiltration depth (cm) (also known as total infiltration depth, or infiltration rate, or cumulative infiltration, or cumulative infiltration depth, or cumulative infiltration rate, or infiltrated water since the beginning of infiltration, or steady state infiltration rate or infiltration time) by length/hour in cm, and the elapsed time (*t*) since the start of infiltration minute or hour, “*a*” and “*b*” are the fitting parameters (constant of empirical adjustment, $a > 0$ and $0 < b < 1$), “*a*” coefficient of infiltration rate, term that depends on the structure and soil conditions ($a > 1$); considered as an index of soil structure stability, “*b*” dimensionless parameter (0 - 1 agricultural soil), a time exponent and is a negative value; considered a measure of first-rate of infiltration and structural condition of the soil (Magnus & Adindu 2014):

$$i = a \cdot t^b \quad (\text{cm}) \quad (1)$$

Kostiakov equation linearization by both equation sides logarithms application. The infiltration “*i*” is normally plotted versus time on a logarithm graph sheet (double-logarithmic scales) and the best-fit line obtained by least-square curve fitting technique. A plot of $\log(i)$ against $\log(t)$, gives a straight line whose slope gives the value of “*b*”, while $\log(a)$ gives the intercept. The value of “*a*” is obtained from the anti- $\log(a)$ (Akinbile 2010, Magnus & Adindu 2014):

$$\text{Log}(i) = \text{log}(a) + b \cdot \text{log}(t) \quad (2)$$

$$a = 10^{\text{log}(a)} \text{equivalent to } a = \text{log}(10^a) \text{ because } a = \text{antilog}(\text{log}(a)) \quad (3)$$

According to Saito *et al.* (2016) constant “*b*” has a negative and strong correlation. This constant does not have clear physical meaning, but when the “*b*” value is small, the infiltration rate rapidly decreases with time. Thus, “*b*” values were particularly small where there are horizons of low permeability. These “*b*” values enhanced the negative slope of the regression line. “*a*” measures infiltrability at the beginning of the infiltration process and results show that surface soil permeability was strongly correlated with the vegetation. Kincaid *et al.* (1969) found for three different soils (silt loam, sandy loam, and clay), that “*a*” ranged from 0.225 to 1.1 and “*b*” from 0.458 to 0.669. According to Al-Azawi (1985), Moroke *et*

al. (2009) and Adindu *et al.* (2014), “*b*” is accepted by most authors less than 1 (Al-Azawi 1985, Moroke *et al.* 2009, Adindu *et al.* 2014). Since the infiltration decreases with time, the exponent “*b*” considered negative; in this work varied $-1 < b < 0$. Analyzing Equation 1, when time tends to infinity, as “*b*” is negative, “*i*” would tend to zero instead of a constant value (different from zero). Fubara-Manuel and Otoko (2015) work in loamy sand soil in Nigeria, found the values of “*a*”, and “*b*”, 0.62 and 0.01 correspondingly. Gosh (1985) questioned, in the model, the value of “*b*” between zero and one. Mathematically, he proved that the value of “*b*” is greater than unity. Mbagwu (1990) experimentally found that the value of “*b*” was consistently less than one. On real field plots, Roy and Gosh (1982) reported that the infiltration rate was neither asymptotic with the time (*t*) axis, nor attained a zero value. Musa and Adeoye (2010) found values of “*b*” that ranged from 0.37 - 1.79, and the infiltration equations obtained for the soils were: $0.41t^{1.38}$, $0.41t^{1.79}$, $0.50t^{0.37}$, $0.42t^{1.12}$ and $0.53t^{1.37}$, soil structure was not included. Soils that have very stable structure have values of “*b*” greater than 0.6 and can reach 1.0 under conditions where gravity flow predominates (Rondón *et al.* 1980).

Concurring to Swartzendruber and Huberty (1958) “*a*” defined as a measure of the average infiltration rate for the first unit time interval, “*b*” is an indicator of the changes in the system of force with time; also, if “*b*” is close to 0.5, assumed that capillary forces are controlling infiltration, and that deviation of “*b*” from 0.5 is a measure of the relative importance of other forces and factors in controlling infiltration; similarly, gravity forces and hydraulic pressures, such as ponding, cause higher values for “*b*”. Swartzendruber and Huberty (1958) and Dixon (1976) exhibited that “*a*” is the storage during the first hour, and “*b*” is the ratio which reflects the degree of storage abatement during the first hour, $b = 1$ indicating no abatement and $b = 0$ complete abatement; also manifested that the size of parameter “*b*” is inversely related to the number and intensity of active infiltration decay processes, and “*a*” is simply product of the first-hour time-weighted means for the hydraulic conductivity and the hydraulic gradient at the soil surface by Darcy's law.

The derivative of Equation 1 yields the instantaneous infiltration rate (*I*) indicating the infiltration depth per unit time *t*. “*I*” represents the rates of change. The second derivative produces the acceleration rate. The infiltration depth rate units are generally in $\text{cm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, multiplied by 60 to convert to $\text{cm}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. The differential represents an infinitely small

change in the variable *i*. It represents the relationship between a continuously varying quantity and its rate of change:

$$I = \frac{di}{dt} = b * a * t^{b-1} \quad (\text{cm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}) \quad (4)$$

$$di = (b * a * t^{b-1}) dt \quad (5)$$

To test the Kostiakov model is necessary to study the basic speed of entry or basic infiltration (least value of *f*(*t*) in a finite time interval); defined as the value, when the rate of change of response for a standard period is 10% or less of its value; i.e., infiltration remains constant, after a certain period (Rode 1965, Holzapfel & Matta 2005, Villalobos 2008, Orjuela-Matta *et al.* 2010):

$$\frac{di}{dt} = -0.1 * i \quad (6)$$

$$I = -0.1 * a * t^b \Rightarrow \quad (7)$$

$$a * b * t^{b-1} = -0.1 * a * t^b \Rightarrow t = -10 * b \quad (8)$$

$$I_{BA} = a * (-10 * b)^b \quad \text{for } i = a * t^b \quad (9)$$

If basic infiltration I_{BA} is in $\text{cm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, multiplied by 60, I_{BA} is obtained in $\text{cm}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. Equation 10 represents the time when the basic infiltration occurs.

$$I_{BA} = a * (-600 * b)^b \quad (\text{cm}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}) \quad (10)$$

Equation 11 represents the infiltration depth; named also, steady state infiltration rate.

$$I_{INT} = i = a * t^b \quad (\text{cm}) \quad (11)$$

Equation 12 represents the total accumulated infiltration (I_{AC}) when integrating *i* with respect to time

$$I_{AC} = \int_0^t i * dt = \int_0^t a * t^b dt$$

An integral ponders an infinite sum of

infinitesimal quantities.

$$I_{AC} = \frac{a}{(b+1)} * t^{b+1} \quad \text{cm} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$$

$$I_{AC} = \frac{a}{60 * (b+1)} * t^{b+1} \quad (\text{cm} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}) \quad (12)$$

Equation 13 represents the average of medium infiltration

$$I_{MED} = \frac{a * t^b}{(b+1)} \quad (\text{cm}) \quad (13)$$

The parameters “*a*” and “*b*” are site specific since they depend on texture, structure, vegetative cover, infiltrometer type, moisture condition, rainfall intensity, permeability, soil surface conditions and properties (Swartzendruber & Huberly 1958, Childs & Bybordi 1969, Smith 1972, Dixon 1976, Al-Azawi 1985, Berndtsson & Larson 1987, Carvalho *et al.* 1999, Moroke *et al.* 2009, Musa & Adeoye 2010, Dagadu & Nimbalkar 2012, Adindu *et al.* 2014, Kelishadi *et al.* 2014). Giffobd (1978) concluded, based on an analysis of data, that it appeared that coefficients in Kostiakov’s equation were related more to vegetation factors than to soil factors. Naeth *et al.* (1991) established that the lower the value of “*b*”, the flatter the slope and thus the lower the rate of decline of infiltration; and the greater the value of “*a*”, the greater the first infiltration value. The equation has no physical basis and is non-homogeneous, but fits very well to the phenomenon of infiltration and has much use in irrigation. The model does not usually give good results for extended periods as observed in practice, which physically is not true and is at odds with the law of Darcy, for a longer time the ground would behave as a saturated medium and “*i*” should have values close to Kostiakov. A weakness of this model is that it does not predict a constant rate and last infiltration (Mbagwu 1994). Fok (1986) showed that the terms “*a*” and “*b*” have physical meanings although several authors have described as empirical. In spite of the weaknesses of the model, many researchers have used the model to study the infiltration processes in soils of the temperate and tropical regions (Lai *et al.* 1980, Bonell & Williams 1986, Mbagwu 1987,

1990). According to Rondón *et al.* (1980, 1985), the equation has been widely used in irrigation, mainly for its work ability; now, several of the equations used in the design of surface irrigation method involve Kostiakov parameters. According to Sonaje (2013), it describes the infiltration well at minor but less right at large times. No physical interpretation is possible of the constants “*a*”, and “*b*” since they can only be obtained from field studies and curve-fitting. They cannot be derived from soil physical properties. This attributed to an empirical equation to implicitly account for the effects of factors not considered by physical equations. Fok (1986) derived a set of infiltration equations of the form in which the constants related to the same soil parameters. Drawbacks to the equation are that the constants are dependent on first field conditions such as moisture content and crusting, and determined for each irrigation event. Also, the infiltration rate does not approach a constant value, at large times, which is a commonly accepted notion about infiltration behavior in infiltration practice (Roger 1993).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling for the experimental analysis performed on a sandy loam savanna soil in Monagas State, Venezuela, situated at a height of 147 meters and geographical coordinates of 9°41'33" north latitude and 63°23' west longitude; with an annual rainfall of 1127 mm and a mean annual temperature of 27.5°C. Under typical savanna vegetation: *Curatella americana* (Dilleniaceae), *Anacardium occidentale*, Straw Hairy (*Trachypogon* and *Axonopas* sp.), *Byrsonimacrassifolia* Malpighiaceae, *Hyptissuaveolens* Lamiaceae, Grasses and Cyperaceae among others. The soil area selected belongs to an Ultisol group of the family Oxic Paleustults Isohipertérmicin virgin soil conditions. Table 1 shows the physical characteristics and organic matter content of the soil. The particle size is in the range established by Rucks *et al.* (2004) and CIVIL2121 (2012). Figure 1 shows the sampling side position. These soils occupy a large Venezuelan agricultural area occupied in the exploitation of many items, with fertilization, such as maize, sorghum, cassava, and pasture. The lab study achieved in the Soil Physical and Mechanical Laboratory of the University of Oriente, Nucleus of Monagas, Juanico; campus located according UTME482908.31 N-1076748.00 and E-482924.24 N-1076752.51.

Table 1. Texture analysis and organic matter, obtained from soil sampling studied (0-15, 15-30 and 45-60 cm) in Jusepín located in Monagas State.

Components	Horizons (cm)			Diameter mm
	0-15 %	15-30 %	45-60 %	
Verycoarse sand	1.01	1.31	0.20	1.41
Coarse sand	6.18	5.71	2.69	0.72
Medium sand	19.1	14.26	13.34	0.37
Fine sand	32.38	24.77	26.33	0.151
Very fine sand	15.0	13.11	15.81	0.07
Total sand	73.67	58.66	58.37	
Silt	16.13	17.14	29.43	0.053
Clay (kaolinite)	10.2	24.2	12.2	0.024
Organic matter	1.20	0.61	0.45	
Textural class	SCL	SCL	SCL	

Source: Labsea, Eudoca, 2010. UDO, Monagas
SCL sandy loam

Figure 1. Sampling side position.

The experimental unit (Fig. 2) fitted by 9 polyvinyl chlorinated cylinders, 6 inches (15.24 cm) in diameter and of 20 cm height. A volume of 2.50 kg soil deposited in the cylinders with different percentage of soil wetness (3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 %), the soil compaction step carried out by three compaction layers providing 0, 13 and 26 strokes per soil layer. Nine steel plates of 20 cm x 20 cm 1 cm thick used for the base of the cylinders to hold the cylinder and prevent the soil out below. Four steel bars welded at

each corner of the griddle to introduce the cylinders between the bars reinforced with iron wire. A rectangular rubber sheet used to prevent soil run off from the bottom of the cylinder. Statistical analysis under a randomized block design with three replications; with two factors: humidity with five levels (3, 6, 9, 12 and 15%) and compaction with three levels (0, 13 and 26 blows). The shear tension measurement obtained with a manual in-situ vane shears tension tester used in the experimental unit.

Figure 2. Experimental unit and Proctor tester.

The Proctor compaction test is a laboratory method of experimentally determining the optimal moisture content at which a given soil type will become most dense and achieve its maximum bulk density. The original test, most commonly called the standard Proctor compaction test (ASTM 2009).

Immediately after finishing cylinder measurements, a piece of tape, stuck in the cylinder wall, with millimeter scale allowed readings height of water more clearly. The cylinders filled with water applied through a plastic cover to avoid soil disturbances of the falling drop of water. The reading of water levels once the cylinder filled. The measurements consisted in determining the sheets of water infiltrated into the cylinders by differences in readings taken for different time intervals ranging between 1 and 60 minutes, with at least 10 readings to keep up the same number of observations and thus the data comparison. In the cylinders, the water permitted to go down less than two centimeters and if the water was very close to this level, extra water to bring it to its maximum level. The regression analyses curve fit and the multiple regression analysis with backward steps were used statistically. The Durbin-Watson statistic tests autocorrelation considered always between 0 and 4. If the Durbin-

Watson statistic is substantially less than 2, there is evidence of positive serial correlation. As a rough rule of thumb, if Durbin-Watson is less than 1.0, there may be cause for alarm. If > 2 , successive error terms are negatively correlated (Montgomery *et al.* 2001).

RESULTS AND DISCUSIONS

The savanna soil samples terra mechanics characteristics used in the experiment represented in Figure 3 elucidating bulk density with respect to compaction blows, soil wetness, and soil depth carried out in the experiment; also, Figure 4 presents the soil shear tension and bulk density with soil wetness relationship. This exhibits influence of soil moisture and spatial variability upon the physical and terra mechanical characteristics of the savanna soil sample employed in the study. Factors affect soil water infiltration. Observe in Figure 4 that at low soil wetness, the shear tension and bulk density practically does not exist, the soils crumble or powder; the soil particle adhesion force (due to water) disappears. Capillary forces can exceed 10 kPa for particles smaller than 0.02 mm and 1 MPa for particles < 0.0002 mm (Santamarina 2001).

Figure 3. Soil bulk density contrasted with compaction blows, soil wetness, and soil depth.

Figure 4. Shear tension and bulk density versus soil wetness for 15 cm soil profile.

The shear stress (τ) versus soil wetness (HU) regression analysis, with 55 total cases, yielded a suitable quadratic model with 79% R^2 , 78% adjusted R^2 and a 0.000 significance. The equation estimated without constant term: $\tau = 19.428 \cdot HU - 1.156 \cdot HU^2$, with 0.000 significance for HU and HU^2 correspondingly. The optimum value of $\tau = 81.63$ kPa for $HU = 8.40\%$. The bulk density (ρ_s) versus soil wetness (HU) regression analysis curve fit, with 55 total cases, yielded a suitable quadratic model with 99% R^2 , 99% adjusted R^2 and 0.000 significance. The equation estimated without

constant term: $\rho_s = 0.338 \cdot HU - 0.015 \cdot HU^2$, with 0.000 significance for HU and HU^2 correspondingly. The optimum value of $\rho_s = 1.90$ g/cm³ for $HU = 11.27\%$.

Soil infiltration related to soil physical and texture acknowledged by many studies. Amin (2005) and Michael (2010) noted that the factors affecting infiltration rate (i) of a soil include, among others, the nature of the soil, humus content, soil surface roughness, moisture content, rainfall intensity, vegetation type and cover, hydraulic characteristics,

and permeability (related to soil texture and structure). Failure to consider adequate the infiltration process may result in non-uniform distribution of water in the field as well as excessive water loss due to deep percolation and runoff. The antecedent water content of the soil influences sorptivity or capacity of a soil to absorb (suck up) water. According to Jagdale and Nimbalkar (2012) different soil conditions affect the soil infiltration rate. Compacted soils due to movement of agricultural machines have a low infiltration rate which is prone to run off generation.

The Kostiakov parameters “*a*” and “*b*” variability effect on infiltration rate in a savanna soil, Figures 5,

Figure 5. The infiltration rate against constants “*a*”, and “*b*”.

Coefficients “*a*” and “*b*”, are different and depend on many factors such as soil type, time, ancient moisture and soil hydraulic conductivity (Harteli 1992, Azad *et al.* 2016). According to Weber and Apestegui (2016), if “*b*” increases, the initial infiltration rate decreases and basic infiltration rate increases; and if “*a*” increases, both the initial rate and the final infiltration increases. High coefficients of Kostiakov model are probably due to high levels of sand (75.7%). The large range of the variation of coefficient “*a*”, demonstrated considerable spatial variability in the study area (Duan *et al.* 2011, Zolfaghari *et al.* 2012, Mirzaee *et al.* 2014, Azad *et al.* 2016). Bresler *et al.* (1984) found that between 24-45% of the variability in “*a*” could be related to the sand content and 10-25% explained by the interaction between electrical conductivity and sand amount. Nestor (2006) found for parameter “*a*”, a value of 76.88 for sandy loam. Adindu *et al.* (2014)

shows a greater influence of “*a*” more than “*b*”. The “*b*” values keep practically steady for each value of “*a*”. The multiple regression analyses for the dependent variable (*i*) and the independent variable *a*, *b*, *a***b*, *a*², *b*² and *a***b*², generated a model that includes parameters *a*, *a***b*, *a*², *b*² and *a***b*² with 0.0000 P significance respectively. The analysis of variance for the model with 0.0000 P significance, 99.98% R², 99.98% adjusted R² and Durbin-Watson 1.43. Figure 5A ratifies a great influence of parameter “*a*” upon the infiltration rate, also revealed in the surface equation. The variability of “*i*” with respect to “*b*” exhibits the same observation in Figure 5A and 5B.

found for the Kostiakov’s infiltration model parameters of some sandy loam soils for “*b*” values of -0.48, -0.50, -0.54, -0.59, -0.62 and -0.84; negatives, indicating that the soils saturated at that time of the year (wet season), while the “*a*” values ranged from 0.35 - 2.47. Girei *et al.* (2016) considered the values of “*a*”, and “*b*” very high in almost across all the treatments. The higher the value of “*b*”, the steeper the slope and the greater the rate of infiltration decline. The greater the value of “*a*” the greater the initial infiltration value (Naeth *et al.* 1991, Turner 2006). The value of “*b*” was consistently less than one. Mbagwu (1990) reported similar findings. Mbagwu (1994) found that the soil properties with greatest influence over the “*a*” term are the effective porosity and bulk density. According to Kanya (2007) the value of “*a*” affects the value of “*b*” depending on the field data. In this work, “*b*” as a function of “*a*”, resulted $b = 5E-07*a^3$

$-0.0002*a^2 + 0.0143*a - 0.3666$ with $R^2 = 0.8021$. Michael (1978), Saxton *et al.* (1986), Mbagwu (1994), Maheshwari (1997), Hunsaker *et al.* (1999), Musa and Nosa (2003), Kanya (2007), Lili *et al.* (2008), Zhuo *et al.* (2009), Azuka *et al.* (2013), Mazloom and Foladmand (2013), Adindu *et al.* (2014) and Arab *et al.* (2014). Al-Azawi (1985) noted that soil infiltrability influenced by soil structure, texture, moisture content, initial water content, structure and surface cover conditions,

organic matter content, bulk density, clay and fine sand content (texture), wheel furrows, season period, hydraulic conductivity and microporosity contributed immensely to the variation in the infiltration characteristics of the soils.

The analysis of variance of Kostiakov parameter “*b*” (Table 2), shows significance with respect to compaction, soil wetness, depth, CO*PR and HU*PR.

Table 2. Constant “*b*”, analysis of variance for block, compaction, soil wetness, soil depth and the combined effect of BL*CO, BL*HU, BL*PR, CO*HU, CO*PR and HU*PR of a soil savanna of Monagas State of Venezuela.

Sources	Constant “ <i>b</i> ”				
	DF	SS	MS	F	P
Block (BL)	2	0.02376	0.01188	1.25	0.2922
Compaction (CO)	2	0.13147	0.06573	6.90	0.0016
SOIL WETNESS (HU)	4	0.63076	0.15769	16.56	0.0000
SOIL DEPTH (PR)	2	0.20237	0.10118	10.63	0.0001
BL*CO	4	0.02206	0.00552	0.58	0.6785
BL*HU	8	0.10931	0.01366	1.43	0.1933
BL*PR	4	0.02206	0.00552	0.58	0.6785
CO*HU	8	0.75621	0.09453	9.93	0.0000
CO*PR	4	0.06578	0.01645	1.73	0.1512
HU*PR	8	0.21516	0.02690	2.82	0.0078
Error	88	0.83802	0.00952		
Total	134	3.03128			
Mean		-0.2016			
CV		-48.41	Alfa: 0.05		

DF (Degree of freedom), SS (Sum of Square), MS (mean sum of squares), *F* (*F*-statistic significance), *P* (*P*-value significance)

The multiple regression analysis for the combined effect CO*HU on the dependent variable “*b*” and the independents variables CO, HU, CO*HU, CO², HU², CO²*HU, CO*HU², CO²*HU², generated a model that includes CO, CO² and CO²*HU² with *P* significance of 0.000, 0.0205 and 0.0011 respectively. The analysis of variance with 0.0000 *P* significance, 92.2% R², 90.79% adjusted R²

and Durbin-Watson 1.02. In the response surface chart of Figure 6, “*b*” with respect to compaction decreased at low wetness; but, increased at higher wetness. “*b*” varies with soil compaction and soil wetness. According to Negro (1998) constant “*b*” gives an idea of the soil water content at the initial process.

Figure 6. Surface response draft of empirical constant “*b*” versus compaction and moisture.

The multiple regression analysis for the combined effect HU*PR on the dependent variable “b” and the independent variable PR, HU, PR*HU, PR², HU², PR²*HU, PR*HU², PR²*HU², generated a model that includes parameters HU, PR and HU*PR with *P* significance of 0.0450, 0.0000 and 0.0005 respectively. The analysis of variance with 0.0000 *P* significance, 94.72% R², 93.83% adjusted R² and

Durbin-Watson 2.29. The equation without constant generated was: $b = -0.00868566*HU - 0.0105247*PR + 0.000728146*HU*PR$. In the response surface chart of Figure 7, “b” with respect to soil wetness and soil depth, with the highest value at 15% water range for all soil depth. It could be supposed that constant “b” highest values indicate high soil humidity.

Figure 7. Surface response draw of constant “b” versus soil wetness and soil depth.

The “b” indicates how the infiltration rate reduces with time; therefore, it depends on the soil structure changes, resulting from wetting. A small value of “b” indicates that the structure is not stable so the infiltration rate reduces due to destruction of the structure.

The analysis of variance of Kostiakov parameter “a” (Table 3), shows significance with respect to compaction, soil wetness, depth, CO*PR, CO*HU and HU*PR.

Table 3. Constant “a”, analysis of variance for block, compaction, soil wetness, soil depth and the combined effect of BL*CO, BL*HU, BL*PR, CO*HUM, CO*PR and HU*PRO of a soil savanna of Monagas State of Venezuela.

Sources	Constant “a”				
	DF	SS	MS	F	P
Block (BL)	2	185	92.5	0.44	0.6448
Compaction (CO)	2	51226	25613.1	122.11	0.0000
SOIL WETNESS (HU)	4	8550	2137.4	10.19	0.0000
SOIL DEPTH (PR)	2	2771	1385.5	6.61	0.0021
BL*CO	4	365	91.4	0.44	0.7826
BL*HU	8	633	79.1	0.38	0.9302
BL*PR	4	706	176.4	0.84	0.5029
CO*HU	8	15120	1890.0	9.01	0.0000
CO*PR	4	9925	2481.2	11.83	0.0000
HU*PR	8	5588	698.5	3.33	0.0023
Error	88	18459	209.8		
Total	134	113527			
Mean	21.931				
CV	66.04	Alfa: 0.05			

DF (Degree of freedom), SS (Sum of Square), MS (mean sum of squares), *F* (*F*-statistic significance), *P* (*P*-value significance)

The multiple regression analysis for the combined effect HU*PR on the dependent variable “a” and the independent variable HU, PR, HU*PR, HU², PR², HU²*PR, HU*PR², HU²*PR², generated a model including HU, HU*PR, HU², HU*PR², HU²*PR and HU²*PR² with *P* significance of 0.001, 0.0015, 0.0003, 0.0026, 0.0022, and 0.0035

respectively. The analysis of variance with 0.0001 *P* significance, 97.08% R², 95.46% adjusted R² and Durbin-Watson 1.89. In the response surface chart of Figure 8, “a” varies with respect to soil wetness and slightly with soil depth, with the highest value at around 15-30 cm depth and 9-12% water content.

$$a = 28.2626*HU - 1.47911*HU*PR - 1.9994*HU^2 + 0.0223972*HU*PR^2 + 0.110408*HU^2*PR - 0.0016*HU^2*PR^2$$

Figure 8. Surface response sketch of constant “a” versus soil wetness and soil depth.

The multiple regression analysis for the combined effect CO*PR on the dependent variable “a” and the independent variable HU, PR, HU*PR, HU², PR², HU²*PR, HU*PR², HU²*PR², generated a model that included PR, CO²*PR, HU*PR² and HU²*PR² with *P* significant values of 0.0000, 0.0021, 0.0001 and 0.0002 respectively. The analysis

of variance with 0.0000 *P* significance, 99.82% R², 99.68% adjusted R² and Durbin-Watson 2.68. In the response surface chart of Figure 9, “a” varies with respect to soil compaction slightly compared to soil depth, with the highest value at 45 cm depth and 0 soil compaction.

$$a = 1.03576*PR - 0.00103333*CO^2*PR - 0.00203549*CO*PR^2 + 0.000072063*CO^2*PR^2$$

Figure 9. Surface response illustration of constant “a” versus compaction level and soil depth.

The multiple regression analysis for the combined effect CO*HU on the dependent variable “*a*” and the independent variable HU, PR, HU*PR, HU², PR², HU²*PR, HU*PR², HU²*PR², generated a model including HU, CO*HU and HU² with *P* significant values of 0.0001, 0.0079 and 0.0036 respectively. The analysis of variance with 0.0002 *P* significance, 82.70% R², 79.55% adjusted R² and

Durbin-Watson 2.15. The equation of the fitted model without constant generated was: $a = 10.68*HU - 1.50*CO*HU - 0.45*HU^2$. In the response surface chart of Figure 10, “*a*” varies with respect to soil compaction slightly compared to soil wetness, with the highest value between 6 and 9% soil wetness and 0 soil compaction levels.

Figure 10. Surface response draft of constant “*a*” versus compaction level and soil wetness.

Results shows that “*a*” and “*b*” Kostiakov terms discloses physical meaning. Fok (1986) showed that the terms of the Kostiakov model have physical meanings even though several authors have described it as empirical. According to Adindu *et al.* (2014), the infiltration decay constants obtained negative, indicating that the saturated soils at that time of the year when the experiments conducted due to much rains. Do not use freely the equations forms adopted in this study in any soil unless the constants characteristic for that particular soil is first determined. The Durbin Watson statistic tests autocorrelation considered resulted suitable.

CONCLUSIONS

The relation between the instantaneous infiltration and compaction, and infiltration and bulk density are inversely proportional. In the studied soil, wetness influenced inversely shear tension. Parameter “*a*” affected infiltration more than “*b*”. Compaction influenced “*b*” more than wetness. Depth influenced “*b*” more than wetness. Wetness influenced “*a*” more than depth. Depth influenced “*a*” more than Compaction. Wetness influenced “*a*”

more than compaction. Soil texture is the property that practically prevailed in influence. Soil texture and soil structure are both properties of the soil that have a profound effect on the behavior of soils. Kostiakov parameters have physical relations to soil texture and structure. The need for a continuous and in-depth study on the applicability and accuracy of infiltration equations cannot be exhausted since equation parameters, and performance, vary for different soils.

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